
Pan-STARRS1 Medium-Deep Field Centers

Field	R.A. (J2000)	Decl. (J2000)
MD00	10.675	41.267
MD01	35.875	-4.250
MD02	53.100	-27.800
MD03	130.592	44.317
MD04	150.000	2.200
MD05	161.917	58.083
MD06	185.000	47.117
MD07	213.704	53.083
MD08	242.787	54.950
MD09	334.188	0.283
MD10	352.312	-0.433
MD11	270.000	66.561

(Table 1) Tonry et al., 2012. Table showing the locations of the various Medium-Deep fields, in Right Ascension and Declination

Pan-STARRS1 Medium-Deep Survey, Typical Cadence

Night	Filter	Exposure Time
1	g_{P1} and r_{P1}	8×113 s each
2	i_{P1}	8×240 s
3	z_{P1}	8×240 s
Repeats...
FM ± 3	y_{P1}	8×240 s

Notes. Observations taken three nights on either side of full moon are done only in the y_{P1} band.

(Table 2) Tonry et al, 2012. Table showing the approximate timeline of observations. We will focus on the g, r, i, and z bands.

ISO

AUTO

ISOCORR

APERTURE

(Figure 1) Diagram illustrating various techniques of performing photometry on a source. We will focus on auto and aperture, noting that isophotal and isocorr are generally used for finding the flux of a non-point source, like a galaxy or a nebula.

(Figure 2) Aperture photometry integrated within $2 \times \text{FWHM}$ v. automatic photometry using elliptical apertures. Plotted for one quarter sky-cell, one out of approximately 2,400 such fields. Wide distribution of points indicates unreliable color photometry for objects fainter than i-band magnitude 21.

(Figure 3) Aperture photometry integrated within $5 \times \text{FWHM}$ v. automatic photometry using elliptical apertures. Plotted for same quarter sky cell as Figure 2, which will be field used for the rest of the paper. Concentration of line indicates good agreement between photometry methods up to around 24 magnitudes in the i-band.

(Figure 4) Total sample of detected sources with no error, plotted r-i v i-z. Points in red represent sources detected in i-band and in z-band but not in r-band. A limit is set on the r-band magnitude for these objects based on the maximum statistically significant r-band magnitude detected.

(Figure 5) Total sample of detected sources with no flags, plotted $r-i$ v $g-r$. Points not detected in r -band by nature are not detected in g -band either, and thus are not included in this plot. Points not detected in g -band, but detected in r -band, are plotted in red. We did not plot points which were detected in neither r -band nor g -band. Seemingly random spread of the points is due to the faintness of the sources, especially in the longer-wavelength color bands, and the difficulties associated with plotting their colors. Due to these difficulties, we will mostly be using $r-i$ versus $i-z$ to characterize stars.

(Figure 6) Plot of extendedness cutoff v number of sources detected. The number of stars does not drop drastically from cutoff .2 to .9, indicating Extendedness is not a reliable parameter to use, especially among faint objects.

(Figure 7) A sample of Figure 2 from Covey et al 2007. The dashed line represents the stellar locus, with contours around it representing increasing sigma uncertainty. Sources taken from SDSS.

(Figure 8) Difference in z-band magnitudes, as a function of PS1 i-z magnitudes. Error in the calibration is less than .01 magnitudes from i-z values 0 to 1. Number of sources drop off drastically after i-z = 0, so large-error calibration is minimal.

(Figure 9) Diagram of method of calculating total standard deviation in classification of a source as a star. Lines represent modeled stellar locus with one-sigma error on either side. Point sources use the modified z-band magnitude for each point, to make up for the differences in the z-band in SDSS and PS1.

(Figure 10) Plot of points that are classified as stars within two sigma deviation, according to cuts made based on distance to the stellar locus. The shape of this curve matches well with the shape of the $i-z$ v $r-i$ (x axis and y axis flipped) stellar locus in the Covey paper, showing good agreement between the SDSS stars and the PS1 stars, as expected.

Table 2
Median Colors

Sp. Type	$N_{\text{SDSS}}^{\text{a}}$	$N_{2\text{MASS}}^{\text{b}}$	$g - r^{\text{c}}$	$r - i$	$i - z$	$z - J$	$J - H$	$H - K_S$
M0	915	259	1.31 (0.16)	0.56 (0.08)	0.33 (0.06)	1.20 (0.25)	0.64 (0.07)	0.16 (0.07)
M1	699	230	1.39 (0.16)	0.73 (0.10)	0.41 (0.08)	1.32 (0.41)	0.62 (0.08)	0.19 (0.08)
M2	1078	689	1.40 (0.13)	0.96 (0.10)	0.53 (0.08)	1.26 (0.18)	0.60 (0.07)	0.22 (0.08)
M3	1220	831	1.41 (0.13)	1.13 (0.11)	0.61 (0.08)	1.30 (0.24)	0.59 (0.06)	0.23 (0.06)
M4	814	522	1.46 (0.15)	1.33 (0.13)	0.71 (0.09)	1.37 (0.15)	0.59 (0.06)	0.25 (0.06)
M5	328	269	1.52 (0.13)	1.62 (0.21)	0.90 (0.13)	1.47 (0.12)	0.59 (0.06)	0.28 (0.07)
M6	359	401	1.56 (0.15)	1.92 (0.14)	1.05 (0.07)	1.61 (0.08)	0.60 (0.06)	0.31 (0.08)
M7	160	352	1.58 (0.16)	2.09 (0.19)	1.14 (0.10)	1.71 (0.10)	0.60 (0.08)	0.34 (0.07)
M8	6	118	1.64 (0.12)	2.56 (0.24)	1.41 (0.13)	1.93 (0.13)	0.63 (0.07)	0.39 (0.08)
M9	4	77	1.87 (0.74)	2.70 (0.20)	1.71 (0.18)	2.15 (0.14)	0.69 (0.09)	0.42 (0.07)

(Table 3) Table 2 of West et al 2011. r-i, g-r, and i-z colors for sub-categories of M-dwarfs, based on SDSS data, along with one sigma errors in parentheses. M-dwarf “boxes” defined by one-sigma ranges in r-i, i-z bands.

(Figure 11) Final cuts on stellar population. Points in black represent points within one sigma of stellar locus. Points in blue represent points between one and two sigma of stellar locus. Points in green represent population of non-detection in r-band with correct i-z cuts.